

Polarographic studies on simple and mixed ligand systems involving cephalosporins

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Differential pulse polarography and cyclic voltammetry have been chosen to follow up the metal-drug interactions at low concentrations in unbuffered solutions. Cephapirin, cefoperazone and cefuroxime form stable coordination compounds with Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} . The stoichiometric ratios of cephapirin versus Zn^{II} or Pb^{II} ions in these compounds are 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 respectively. Cefoperazone gives one weak complex of molar ratio 1 : 1 with Zn^{II} ions, but it reacts with Pb^{II} ions forming two types of stable complexes of ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. One complex 1 : 1 species occurs between cefuroxime and Pb^{II} but three complexes appear with Zn^{II} .

The formation constants of the metal ions with a mixture of cephalosporin and glycine ligands are determined. Mixed ligand complexes with molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 [metal : gly : cephal] were observed for the all systems, except cefuroxime with Zn^{II} ions which gave 1 : 1 : 2 complex. The formation of 2 : 1 : 1 complexes did not occur for all studied cephalosporins.

Cephapirin, cefoperazone and cefuroxime are first, second and third generation semi-synthetic cephalosporin derivatives, respectively. They are widely used in clinical therapy for the treatment of severe infections¹. Polarography and other voltammetric methods are important in the characterization of the equilibria existing in the coordinated systems, particularly those involving ligands of biological and pharmaceutical significance. Cephalosporins are electrochemically active, and there are several studies on their polarographic properties^{2,3}. Methodology previously applied for the coordination studies with β -lactam ring compounds includes potentiometric⁴ and spectrophotometric⁵ methods.

In the present work, we report the polarographic analysis of simple complexes of the above cephalosporins with Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions as well as their mixed ligand complexes with glycine.

Results and Discussion

The differential pulse polarographic behavior of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ solutions of the investigated compounds in aqueous unbuffered 0.01 M $NaClO_4$ was determined. According to the present work, as well as the data obtained in the literature^{3,6}, cephapirin exhibits one peak but for cefoperazone and cefuroxime, two peaks are observed. The d.c. polarographic limiting current increased linearly with the square-

Table 1. Variation of the peak potential (E_p , V versus $Ag/AgCl/KCl$) and the peak current (I_p , μA) as a function of the ligand concentration $[X]$ in the presence of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ of metal(II) ions

$[X]$ $10^{-5} M$	Cephapirin				Cefoperazone				Cefuroxime	
	Zn^{II}		Pb^{II}		Zn^{II}		Pb^{II}		Pb^{II}	
	$-E_p$	$-I_p$	$-E_p$	$-I_p$	$-E_p$	$-I_p$	$-E_p$	$-I_p$	$-E_p$	$-I_p$
2	0.948	2.143	0.335	1.870	0.960	3.30	0.341	1.900	0.340	1.860
2	0.950	2.375	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3	—	—	0.335	1.800	0.967	3.650	0.346	1.550	0.347	1.765
5	0.970	3.080	0.340	1.628	—	—	—	—	—	—
7	—	—	—	—	0.975	3.750	0.351	1.790	0.356	1.760
9	—	—	0.359	1.834	0.983	4.00	0.379	2.150	0.360	1.751
10	0.982	3.375	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
13	—	—	0.360	1.751	—	—	—	—	0.364	1.702
14	0.995	3.950	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
15	—	—	—	—	0.984	4.620	0.379	2.250	—	—
19	1.004	4.085	0.366	2.143	0.988	4.183	0.380	2.600	0.371	1.588
23	—	—	0.380	3.073	—	—	—	—	—	—
24	1.010	4.102	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
29	—	—	—	—	1.002	4.238	0.381	3.150	—	—

root of the mercury height, demonstrating that the reduction is diffusion-controlled.

The complexation reaction has been investigated by

R₁ R₂

Cephapirin

Cefuroxime

Cefoperazone

measuring both potential and current evolution of the differential pulse polarographic peak of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} solutions by increasing concentrations of the ligands from 1×10^{-5} to $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ (Table 1). Cephapirin, cefoperazone and cefuroxime are shown to be able to complex Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} ions as indicated by the potential shift and the current decrease of their DPP peaks. Half-peak width values of 64 ± 2 mV are in close agreement with a reversible two-electron process as mentioned elsewhere⁷ using a pulse amplitude of 50 mV. This reversibility has been confirmed by cyclic voltammetry, the difference between the cathodic and the anodic peak potentials being

very close⁸ to $0.059/n$ V.

Zn^{II}-cephalosporin simple and mixed complexes : In order to investigate the complex formation and calculate the stability constants, the reduction potential is plotted against the logarithm of the ligand concentration. This gives rise to a smooth curve (Fig. 1) for cephapirin and cefuroxime, indicating that consecutive complexes are formed between Zn^{II} ions and these ligands. By applying the method of Deford and Hume⁹ modified by Health and Hefter¹⁰, the following functions have been calculated :

$$F_1(x) = \frac{F_0(x) - 1}{[x]}, F_2(x) = \frac{F_1(x) - \beta_1}{[x]}, \dots, \dots, \dots$$

$$F_n(x) = \frac{F_{n-1}(x) - \beta_{n-1}}{[x]} \quad (1)$$

where [x] is the ligand concentration. The diffusion coefficient of the metal-complex is the same as that for the metal only. By plotting $F_0(x)$ function, which includes all the complexes originally present in the solution, and successively $F_1(x)$, $F_2(x)$,..... against the ligand concentration, the stability constants can be determined from the intercepts. The functions are derived until a straight-line parallel to the X-axis is obtained. This last function represents the stoichiometrically highest complex formed in the solution. It can be concluded that three complexes are formed between cephapirin or cefuroxime and Zn^{II} ions with stoichiometries 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 metal-to-ligand. On the other hand, Zn^{II} ions react with cefoperazone and the plot of the potential evolution (Table 1) against the logarithm of the ligand concentration shows a straight-line (Fig. 1, curves A), indicating the formation of only one complex with ratio 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand. A coordination number of 1 is calculated from the slope of the straight-line, corresponding to a 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand complex, its stability constant is obtained using the Lingan's equation¹¹. The logarithmic values of the overall stability constants are reported in Table 2. They are very close to that obtained by the potentiometric measurements performed for 1 : 1 complexes⁴.

At concentration of ligand higher than $2 \times 10^{-5} M$, an enhancement in the current was noticed, which renders more of Zn^{II} ions reduced due to adsorption of the formed complexes at the electrode-solution interface.

For the mixed ligand complexes involving cephalosporin derivatives and glycine, it is found from the results of the simple systems that stability constants of the complexes with glycine are higher than those of Zn^{II}-cephalo-

Table 2. The logarithmic values of the overall stability constants for the formed binary and ternary complexes with Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} in presence of cephalosporin derivatives and glycine

Formation constant	Cephapirin		Cefoperazone		Cefuroxime		Formation constant	Glycine	
	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}		Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
log β ₀₁	04.060	03.813	0.431	4.193	03.100	04.352	log β ₁₀	4.623	4.000
log β ₀₂	07.422	07.079	-	7.989	05.954	-	log β ₂₀	8.580	8.875
log β ₀₃	10.294	12.301	-	-	10.519	-	log β ₃₀	12.061	13.1
log β ₁₁	08.903	10.165	9.747	9.635	-	10.082	-	-	-
log β ₁₂	-	-	-	-	09.022	-	-	-	-

Table 3. Variation of the peak potential (E_p , V versus Ag/AgCl/KCl) and the peak current (I_p , μA) as a function of the ligand concentration $[X]$ in the presence of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ of metal(II) ions

$[X]$ $10^{-5} M$	Cephapirin				Cefoperazone				Cefuroxime			
	Zn^{II}		Pb^{II}		Zn^{II}		Pb^{II}		Zn^{II}		Pb^{II}	
	$-E_p$	$-I_p$										
1	0.923	1.900	0.351	1.959	-	-	0.365	2.437	0.950	2.143	0.356	1.291
2	0.950	1.750	0.361	1.747	0.948	2.176	0.386	2.208	0.950	2.045	0.359	1.215
4	0.961	1.000	0.381	1.388	0.961	0.871	-	-	0.960	1.646	0.380	0.982
8	0.983	0.750	0.390	1.421	0.977	0.818	0.393	1.037	0.976	0.849	0.391	0.209
10	0.990	0.630	0.400	1.084	0.992	0.664	0.402	0.820	0.979	0.729	0.391	0.166
16	0.999	0.755	0.411	0.852	1.002	0.916	-	-	0.990	0.795	-	-
20	1.008	0.765	0.421	0.603	1.006	0.866	-	-	0.998	0.796	-	-
30	1.011	0.765	0.421	0.416	1.022	0.909	-	-	1.008	0.851	-	-
40	1.018	0.900	-	-	1.034	0.681	-	-	1.010	0.985	-	-

sporins complexes. This behavior may be interpreted based on the bidentate nature of glycine which coordinates through the α -amino nitrogen and the carboxylic oxygen

Fig. 1. Peak potential evolution as a function of the logarithm of the ligand concentration in the presence of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ metal ions for simple complexes : (a) Zn-cephapirin, (b) Zn-cefoperazone, (c) Zn-cefuroxime, (d) Pb-cephapirin, (e) Pb-cefoperazone and (f) Pb-cefuroxime; unbuffered medium NaClO_4 , $\mu = 0.01$, temp. = 25° .

atoms forming stable five-membered chelate ring, unlike the cephalosporin ligands which may be coordinated through the carboxylate group, 8-carbonyl group and amino nitrogen atom moieties leading to the formation of six-membered rings. It is well known that $3d$ -metal ions prefer five-membered to six-membered rings during chelations. The ternary complexes were investigated by running two sets of experiments, each one at a fixed concentrations of cephalosporin, 1×10^{-5} and $4 \times 10^{-5} M$, chosen so that Zn^{II} -cephalosporin complex would contain predominantly one or four cephalosporins ions per metal ion. Therefore, glycine is chosen as the primary ligand and cephalosporin as the secondary one. On adding glycine (as primary ligand) to the solution containing Zn^{II} and cephalosporin (fixed), the DPP peak shifted to negative potentials, larger than the shift obtained for either of simple systems at the same metal, and the current decreases, indicating formation

Fig. 2. Peak potential evolution as a function of the logarithm of the ligand concentration in the presence of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ metal ion and $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ cephalosporin for mixed ligand complexes : (a) Zn-gly-cephapirin, (b) Zn-gly-cefoperazone, (c) Zn-gly-cefuroxime, (d) Pb-gly-cephapirin, (e) Pb-gly-cefoperazone and (f) Pb-gly-cefuroxime; unbuffered medium NaClO_4 , $\mu = 0.01$,

of a ternary complexes (Table 3 and Fig. 1, curves B). Furthermore, the electrode process remained reversible involving two electrons. The different functions F_{ij} were calculated by the method of Schaap and McMasters¹² (Table 4) as well as the constants A , B , C and D by Leden's¹³ extrapolation method (Fig. 2). From the values of B at the two different cephalosporins concentrations, the formation constants of Zn^{II} complexes with stoichiometric ratios $1 : 1 : 1$ and $1 : 1 : 2$ have been determined (Table 2). It can be seen that cephapirin and cefoperazone from $1 : 1 : 1$ complexes only, but cefuroxime forms $1 : 1 : 2$ species. Furthermore, no complexation with ratios $1 : 2 : 1$ occurred under our experimental conditions.

Pb^{II}-cephalosporin simple and mixed complexes : The complex formation is evidenced by the negative shift of the

peak potential and the decrease of the current observed when cephalosporin or cefoperazone is added to a $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ lead solution. The data are shown in Table 1 and Fig 1, curves A. The plots of $F_n(x)$ functions against $[x]$, which represents the ligand concentration, yield curves with intercepts

Table 4. Derived $F_n(X)$ functions for the zinc/lead-gly-cephapirin systems*

$10^{-5} [X]$ M	$\log(I_p)_s / (I_p)_c$	$-\Delta E_p$ mV	$F_{00}(X)$	$10^4 F_{10}$ (X)	$10^8 F_{20}$ (X)	$10^{12} F_{30}$ (X)
Zn-Gly-cephapirin system :						
1	0.026	02.4	01.152	045.20	092.00	05.200
2	0.061	09.5	01.587	044.35	041.75	08.750
3	0.185	15.5	02.420	057.33	071.10	10.367
4	0.304	21.4	03.25	068.13	080.31	10.078
5	0.334	26.8	04.840	082.80	093.60	10.720
6	0.363	32.1	06.600	098.33	103.88	10.647
7	0.395	37.4	08.800	115.72	113.88	10.554
8	0.429	42.7	11.392	133.65	122.06	10.258
9	0.465	46.3	14.300	151.11	127.90	09.768
10	0.505	49.9	17.314	166.14	130.14	09.011
Pb-Gly-cephapirin system :						
1	0.157	20.5	02.873	08.730	—	—
2	0.207	31.5	04.630	13.150	05.750	26.25
4	0.307	50.8	07.314	13.285	03.213	6.783
6	0.351	55.1	10.500	14.167	03.612	5.187
8	0.397	59.7	14.942	16.178	05.223	5.904
10	0.414	70.3	21.00	19.000	07.000	6.500
12	0.449	73.9	28.800	22.333	08.611	6.759
14	0.483	77.5	38.200	25.857	09.898	6.713
16	0.519	81.0	51.223	30.764	11.728	7.018
18	0.595	85.9	70.300	37.944	14.413	7.729
20	0.669	90.8	100.81	49.405	18.703	9.101

$[Zn^{II}]$ or $[Pb^{II}] = 1 \times 10^{-5} M$, unbuffered medium $NaClO_4$, $\mu = 0.01$, temp. = 25° .

β_n 's, the latter yields a straight-line parallel to the $[x]$ X-axis. Smooth curves were observed in case of cephalosporin and cefoperazone in presence of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ Pb^{II} ions, indicating that consecutive complexes are formed under our experimental conditions. The logarithmic values of the overall stability constants are reported in Table 2. It can be concluded that three complexes are formed between Pb^{II} and cephalosporin with ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3, while two complexes with ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 appear with cefoperazone. On the other hand, Pb^{II} ions react with cefuroxime and the plot of the potential evolution against the logarithm of the ligand concentration gives rise to a straight-line indicating the formation of only one complex species with ratio 1 : 1. A coordination number of 1 is calculated from the slope of this straight-line, corresponding to a 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand complex, its stability constant being obtained using the Langan's equation¹¹. The values of $\log \beta$ of Pb^{II} -cephalosporins complexes are very close to that obtained by the potentiometric measurements⁴ performed for 1 : 1 complexes. Also, it appears that at concentration higher than $7 \times 10^{-5} M$ of cephalosporin or cefoperazone, increase in the current was observed which may be attributed to the adsorption of their complexes at the electrode surface.

The mixed ligand complexes involving cephalosporin and glycine, were investigated using the same procedure

with Zn^{II} . The increasing addition of glycine to the solutions of simple complexes with cephalosporin gives rise to a negative shift of the peak potentials and a decrease of the current (Table 3 and Fig. 1, curves B). The functions (F_n) were calculated (Table 4) and also the constants A , B , C and D . From the values of B , the formation constants of mixed ligand complexes of Pb^{II} with stoichiometric ratios 1 : 1 : 1 have been determined (Table 2). It can be seen that no complexation between these ligands and Pb^{II} with ratios 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 were observed.

It is obvious from the above results that it is easier for cephalosporin derivatives to add to $[M(II)$ -glycine] than to $[M(II)$ -cephalosporin], thus formation of ternary complexes are more favoured than the binary ones. Thus, the importance mixed ligand complexes can be ascribed to its application as models for metalloenzyme complexes and also as components of the multimetal-multiligand systems in biological fluid.

Experimental

The semi-synthetic cephalosporin derivatives (Sigma) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Aqueous stock solution (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) of the drugs were prepared in triple-distilled water. Before and during measurements, solutions were kept at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. All experiments were performed at $pH 7.4 \pm 0.1$ and the ionic strength was maintained constant at $0.01 M$ with $NaClO_4$. An Amel 433A polarographic analyser was used. All potentials are referred to a saturated reference electrode. For differential pulse polarographic experiments, forced drop time of 1 s, scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} and pulse height of 50 mV were applied. For cyclic voltammetric operations, a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} was used. At the start of each experiment, the solution in the measurement cell (10 ml) was purged with purified N_2 gas for about 30 min.

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